

Electrochromatographic Separation of Amino Acids on Inorganic Ion-Exchange Papers

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Manuscript received 12 May 1978, accepted 10 July 1978

Electrochromatography of twenty-eight amino acids have been performed on papers impregnated with stannic arsenate, an inorganic ion-exchanger, using fifteen different solvent systems. Effect of non-aqueous medium and dielectric constant of eluent on the movement of amino acids in electric field are discussed. Numerous analytically and bio-chemically important binary and ternary separations have been achieved.

THE identification and separation of amino acids contained in mixtures presents considerable interest in several fields such as : in the control of drug purity in biological sciences, in toxicology, pharmacology, forensic, medicine, etc. For this reason it was decided to approach this subject in connection with a mixture of compounds representing different types of amino acids. Earlier studies on paper impregnated with stannic arsenate were applied for separation of amino acids by paper chromatography¹. Effect of *pH* and molecular weight of side chain on *R_F* values were discussed. In the present communication, the effect of non-aqueous solvents and dielectric constant on the movement of amino acids in electric field are discussed.

Methods and Materials :

Apparatus : Ion-exchange papers were prepared by loading stannic arsenate on Whatman 3 mm filter paper strips size 36 × 3 cm, using Shandon electrophoresis vertical tank. A Sargent oscilometer type (V) was used for dielectric constant measurements.

Reagents and Chemicals : Stannic chloride pentahydrate (Poland) and sodium arsenate Riedel (Germany) were used. The following amino acids used were synthesized in these laboratories :

(a) β -Amino- β (*o*-benzene carboxylic) alanine, (b) β -(*p*-Dimethyl aminophenyl) alanine, (c) β -(*m*-Aminophenyl) alanine, (d) β -(1-Naphthyl) alanine, (e) β -Piperonyl alanine, (f) 3,4-Dihydroxyphenyl alanine, (g) δ,δ -Dimethyl isoleucine, (h) β -Hydroxy- α -amino adipic acid, (i) δ -(*o*-Aminophenyl) norvaline, (j) Cyclohexyl glycine. Other amino acids studied were : α -Alanine, β -alanine, phenylalanine, glycine, cyclopentyl glycine, N-phenylglycine, glycyglycine, leucine, asparagine, aspartic acid, glutamic acid, citrulline, methionine, lysine, histidine, tyrosine, serine, creatine, tryptophan, proline, cystine and valine, all of analar grade.

All other reagents were of analar grade and were obtained either from BDH (England) or from E. Merck (Darmstadt).

Preparation of Ion-exchange papers : Whatman 3 mm paper strips of required size were dipped in 0.1M stannic chloride solution for 3 to 5 seconds, removing the excess of reagent by placing the strips over a filter paper sheet and allowing to dry for 15 minutes at room temperature. The strips were then dipped in 0.25M sodium arsenate solution for 15 seconds. The excess solution was drained off and strips were placed over filter sheet. These strips were dried at room temperature and then washed with demineralized water three times to remove the excess reagents. Finally, these were dried at room temperature and used for electrochromatography.

Amino acid Solutions : Stock solutions of amino acids (0.2%) were made in aqueous propanol (10% V/V), a minimum quantity of acetic acid was added in the case of cyclohexyl glycine.

Detection Reagent : A 2% solution of ninhydrin in 1-butanol saturated with water was used for locating the spots of amino acids on paper. Solvent systems used for electrochromatographic development : The following solvents were used as eluents for electrophoresis :

1. Acetic acid + Formic acid + Water (15+10+950).

Applied potential = 300V, time = 4 hr,
(*pH* 2.0).

2. Formic acid + Propionic acid + Water (10+15+950).

Applied potential = 350V, Time = 4 hr,
(*pH* 2.7).

3. Formic acid+Water (250+750).
Applied potential=100V, Time=4 hr.
4. Formic acid+Water (333+666).
Applied potential=100V, Time=4 hr.
5. Formic acid+Water (500+500).
Applied potential=100V, Time=4 hr.
6. Phthalate buffer (pH 4.0).
Applied potential=250V, Time 4.30 hr.
7. Phosphate tartrate buffer (pH 1.7).
Applied potential=350V, Time=4 hr.
8. Phosphate tartrate buffer (pH 4.0).
Applied potential=300V, Time=5 hr.
9. Phosphate tartrate buffer (pH 6.5),
Applied potential=250V, Time=5 hr.
10. Phosphate tartrate buffer (pH 6.0).
Applied potential=200V, Time=5 hr.
11. Phosphate tartrate buffer (pH 3.5).
Applied potential=200V, Time 5 hr.
12. Phosphate tartrate buffer (pH 5.4).
Applied potential=100V, Time=5 hr.
13. Pyridine+Water (250+750).
Applied potential=300V, Time=5 hr.
14. Acetic acid+Water (250+750).
15. Ethanol+Water (250+750).
Applied potential=300V, Time=5 hr.

Procedure : The electrophoresis apparatus was filled to the mark with background electrolyte and stannic arsenate loaded ion-exchange strips, which formed the stabilization medium were placed in position and allowed to become saturated with the electrolyte concerned. Then a streak of the test solution (0.02 ml) was applied separately on each strip in the middle with the help of thin glass capillaries. The time of migration and the potential applied is specified in each case. The migration zones of amino acids towards anode or cathode was measured from the point of application up to the middle of the zone. On the basis of the results of explanatory experiments and distance of electrical migration of the zones of individual amino acids, synthetic mixtures of particular amino acids were applied as in the case of individual amino acid for separation.

Results

The movement of amino acids in electric field at appropriate potential was studied in fifteen different solvent systems. The distance of the centre of the detected spot from the starting line was taken as a measure of movement. The movement of amino acids towards anode and cathode is represented by positive and negative signs respectively. On the basis of the difference of movement of amino acids in different solvent systems various separations were tried.

Numerous binary and ternary separations achieved practically are listed in Table 1.

TABLE 1—EXPERIMENTALLY ACHIEVED SEPARATIONS OF AMINO ACIDS ON STANNIC ARSENATE PAPERS BY ELECTROCHROMATOGRAPHY

Sl. No.	Separation	From	Solvent system used
<i>Binary separations</i>			
1.	Asparagine (+1.0)	Lysine (-0.9)	1
2.	Asparagine (+1.0)	Glycine (-0.8)	1
3.	Asparagine (+1.0)	Histidine (-2.2)	2
4.	Asparagine (+0.9)	δ -(<i>o</i> -Aminophenyl) norvaline (-1.2)	2
5.	Asparagine (+1.0)	Serine (-1.3)	2
6.	Asparagine (+1.0)	Tyrosine (-1.4)	2
7.	Leucine (0.0)	Valine (+1.1)	2
8.	Citrulline (0.0)	Histidine (-2.0)	2
9.	Tyrosine (-1.5)	Valine (+1.0)	2
10.	Tryptophan (+0.7)	Tyrosine (-1.6)	2
11.	Histidine (-2.0)	Valine (+1.0)	2
12.	Citrulline (-0.5)	Lysine (-2.4)	2
13.	Methionine (-0.8)	β -Alanine (-3.0)	3
14.	Valine (-1.0)	β -Alanine (-3.0)	3
15.	α -Alanine (-1.0)	β -Alanine (-2.8)	3
16.	Tyrosine (-0.5)	β -Alanine (-3.1)	3
17.	Tyrosine (-0.5)	Lysine (-2.4)	3
18.	Citrulline (-0.6)	Proline (-2.3)	4
19.	Tryptophan (-1.5)	α -Alanine (-3.1)	5
20.	Phenyl alanine (0.0)	N-Phenyl glycine (-2.5)	5
21.	Valine (-1.0)	α -Alanine (-3.0)	5
22.	Aspartic Acid (-1.2)	α -Alanine (-2.9)	5
23.	Cystine (0.0)	Histidine (-3.2)	6
24.	Asparagine (+0.8)	Proline (-1.8)	6
25.	Asparagine (+0.9)	β -Alanine (-1.9)	6
26.	Aspartic Acid (+0.5)	δ -(<i>o</i> -Aminophenyl) norvaline (-3.4)	6
27.	Tyrosine (-0.5)	δ -(<i>o</i> -Aminophenyl) norvaline (-3.5)	6
28.	N-Phenyl glycine (-4.2)	Glycine (-1.8)	7
29.	Lysine (-4.3)	Tryptophan (-2.0)	7
30.	Aspartic Acid (-0.9)	Lysine (-4.0)	7
31.	Lysine (-4.4)	Glutamic Acid (+1.8)	8
32.	Glutamic Acid (+1.8)	Tryptophan (-1.6)	8
33.	Glutamic Acid (+1.9)	β -alanine (-2.2)	8
34.	Glutamic Acid (+1.9)	Histidine (-2.4)	8
35.	Aspartic Acid (+0.8)	Proline (-2.6)	8
36.	Aspartic Acid (+1.0)	β -Alanine (-2.2)	8
37.	Glutamic Acid (-1.0)	Aspartic Acid (+2.0)	9
38.	Aspartic Acid (+1.9)	Tryptophan (-1.5)	9
39.	Aspartic Acid (+2.0)	Citrulline (-2.4)	9
40.	Serine (0.0)	α -Alanine (-1.6)	9
41.	Aspartic Acid (+2.0)	Histidine (-2.7)	9
42.	Aspartic Acid (+2.0)	Phenylalanine (0.0)	9
43.	Aspartic Acid (+2.1)	Proline (-2.0)	9
44.	Tyrosine (-1.6)	β -Alanine (+1.1)	9
45.	α -Alanine (-1.5)	β -Alanine (+1.0)	9
<i>Ternary separations</i>			
46.	Glycine (-1.8)	Valine (+1.0) and Phenyl alanine (0.0)	2
47.	Aspartic Acid (+0.6)	Citrulline (-1.0) and Histidine (-3.0)	6
48.	Cystine (0.0)	Asparagine (+0.8) and Valine (-1.5)	6
49.	Asparagine (+0.6)	Citrulline (-1.0) and Histidine (-3.0)	6
50.	Citrulline (-1.5)	Asparagine (+1.4) and Lysine (-4.4)	8
51.	Asparagine (0.0)	Aspartic Acid (+2.0) and Lysine (+3.1)	9
25.	Valine (-0.6)	Aspartic Acid (+1.9) and Histidine (-2.5)	9

Effect of formic acid as non-aqueous solvent on the movement of amino acids was observed, the results are plotted in Fig. 1.

The results of dielectric constant as a function of movement of amino acid in electric field are presented in Fig. 2.

Fig. 1. Plot of movement of Amino acid Vs Formic acid contents

Fig. 2. Plot of movement of Amino acids as a function of dielectric constant.

Discussion

The papers impregnated with stannic arsenate are particularly useful for the separation of amino acids and are extremely selective and give fast and clean separations¹. The results of the paper electrochromatographic studies show that numerous analytically and bio-chemically important separations can be achieved using different solvent systems. A few examples are alanine from serine, alanine from valine and glutamic acid from aspartic acid (Table 1).

Silk fibroin contains large amount of alanine, serine, valine and methionine. The separation of

alanine from serine and methionine from β -alanine were achieved can be applied for the analysis of silk fibroin.

Separation of glutamic acid from aspartic acid was achieved in phosphate tartarate buffer (pH 6.5) at 250V in 5 hr. The importance of this separation is:

(a) glutamic acid is higher homologue of aspartic acid.

(b) both glutamic and aspartic acid are present in large amounts in blood.

Similarly leucine is a higher homologue of valine and can be separated using formic acid+propionic acid+water as solvent. Alanine and valine showing similar chemical properties are easily separated in formic acid+water system.

Other interesting point emerges for the study of the movement of amino acids in electric field is that the movement of all amino acids towards the cathode decreases as the concentration of non-aqueous solvent in the background electrolyte increases.

It was also observed that the movement of amino

acids increases as the dielectric constant of the background electrolyte increases.

Acknowledgement

We thank Prof. W. Rahman for research facilities.

Reference

1. J. P. RAWAT, S. Q. MUJTABA and P. S. THIND, *Chem. Anal. (Warsaw)*, 1976, 21, 1235.